

Map of the established relationships between different actors and citizens:

A baseline inventory of social networks at Urbanplanen to shed light on best practices in engaging and listening to diverse voices in the planning and management of urban green infrastructure.

Deliverable D2.3

Photo courtesy of the Partnerskabet, Urbanplanen.

The logo for VIVA PLAN features a stylized graphic on the left consisting of a red outline of a house-like shape, a green square, and a blue outline of a house-like shape. To the right of this graphic, the word "VIVA" is written in red and "PLAN" is written in blue, both in a bold, sans-serif font.

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Led by the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, VIVA-PLAN involves six institutions in fields including urban governance, ecology, landscape architecture, geography and natural resource management. We will draw on multiple methods to assess the co-benefits and costs of nature-based solutions, including green spaces and meeting spots, in vulnerable residential housing areas in cities in Sweden and Denmark. Project results may support the creation of sustainable spatial planning frameworks that promote biodiversity conservation, social inclusion and well-being (including safety and security) in cities in Sweden, Denmark and other parts of the globe.

Authors

Gulsrud, N.M.

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Contents

1	Introduction.....	1
2	Main Findings.....	2
3	Implications of findings for sustainable spatial planning.....	3
4	References.....	3

1 Introduction

Engaging diverse social networks in the planning and management of urban green infrastructure (UGI) is critical for the just and inclusive governance of urban blue and green spaces. Social network analysis in UGI governance is traditionally used to identify and map relations between people and governance systems through quantitative assessments focused on density of social relations through ties and nodes (Nunan, 2015; Örjan Bodin et al., 2011). Yet some, such as Adams et al., (2018), have challenged this purely quantitative approach by suggesting that it masks the need to assess power relations in social networks and governance regimes. Along these lines, there is a need to better understand how diverse resident and actor networks relate to the nested layers of UGI governance (Buijs et al., 2018, 2016). How are residents empowered and/or disempowered in the context of UGI planning and management? What are the preferences for residents and diverse actors for being involved in the future management of urban green spaces and green initiatives?

In VIVA-PLAN we have worked to identify established relationships between diverse actors and residents in a social network analysis to shed light on best practices in engaging and listening to diverse voices in the planning and management of UGI. Here, we have had a specific focus on mapping social networks (Figure 1) linking to issues of residential social inclusion and exclusion in the planning and management of urban green spaces.

This analysis of resident and actor relations draws on data collected in the socially and economically diverse Copenhagen neighborhood of Urbanplanen from November 2019 to November 2020. Urbanplanen, one of Copenhagen's and Denmark's largest cohesive social housing residential areas, aims to open up both socially and physically to the rest of Copenhagen through nature-based solutions for climate adaptation and social cohesion. Urbanplanen houses approximately 6.000 residents and the 450-hectare site has 50 hectares of public urban green spaces.

Figure 1: Social networks in the VIVA-PLAN case sites are divided into four general categories linked to the planning and management of UGI and other green initiatives: (1) Experts such as planners, politicians and professionals, (2) Formally organized resident groups, (3) Individual residents and local champions, (4) Difficult to reach groups such as marginalized youth. As the figure illustrates, these networks are seldom isolated but rather are linked in complex and overlapping ways.

Additionally, we mapped green initiatives in our case sites within the nested networks of green governance (Figure 2). We emphasize questions of environmental justice including preferences for involvement, empowerment in decision making, and overall sense of safety and security. The nested networks of green

governance in Urbanplanen, Copenhagen are divided into four layers moving from the very local to national: (1) Urbanplanen has over 70 active resident groups involved in formal and informal initiatives many of which are green; (2) The Partnership program at Urbanplanen is a social masterplan to support social and ecological development. In spirit, the project is driven by close partnerships between social workers and local grassroots initiatives, yet the success of the masterplan is evaluated on measures of safety, employment, education, and criminality informed by national policies; (3) The City of Copenhagen is committed to increasing the amount and quality of urban nature to support more green meeting places while meeting climate adaptation goals. Engaging unemployed and under-skilled residents in the job market is a top municipal priority and marginalized neighborhoods such as Urbanplanen are in focus; (4) The Danish State “Ghetto plan” is a public housing policy that targets neighborhoods such as Urbanplanen that do not meet state-set performance criteria around income, percentage of employment, levels of education, and proportion of residents with criminal conviction (<https://www.regeringen.dk/publikationer-og-aftaletekster/%C3%A9t-danmark-uden-parallelsamfund/>). If a public housing area does not meet the state-set performance criteria for more than 5 years, the state can mandate the partial demolition and or sale of public housing buildings. This law specifically targets public housing areas where more than 50% of residents are immigrants or descendants of non-Western countries and is therefore currently being legally challenged under the EU’s Race Equality Directive and the European Convention on Human Rights (Open Society Justice Initiative, 2020). This law shapes social policy and by proxy ecological initiatives at Urbanplanen and has the potential to physically and socially transform all low-income, working-class, refugee and immigrant housing areas in Denmark. In December 2020, Hørgården, a housing block in Urbanplanen, was removed from the Ghetto list, yet many housing areas across Denmark remain on this list. Additionally, the state mandates that all municipalities, such as Copenhagen, have a climate adaptation plan (Hansen, 2008) and this mandate informs the overall management and planning of UGI at the municipal level, including the public green spaces in Urbanplanen.

Figure 2: The nested networks of green governance in Urbanplanen

2 Main Findings

Overarching results from our social network analysis reveal that residents and diverse actors are working together to adapt to and re-author social and ecological policies at all levels of green governance in Urbanplanen: (1) to give more power to residents in decision making and (2) to increase their overall safety, security, and wellbeing. The majority of green initiatives at the local level are vehicles for social cohesion as well as political resistance. Specifically, social and political networks at the local and district level coordinate efforts to create collective approaches to re-employment schemes, providing “safe spaces” for more vulnerable and marginalized residents. These approaches are based on an ethics of care and an inclusive community (Harcourt, 2014).

The main findings of this field study to date are:

- Local **“Networks of care”** drive and support district and municipal green partnerships and initiatives.
- Municipal and State employment **directives are re-authored by grassroots groups to fit and serve the relational needs** of local residents.
- Local **relational values are key to long-term management of UGI** including the scaling out and up of NBS.

3 Implications of findings for sustainable spatial planning

Cities are seen as sites of environmental challenges but also as critical sites of environmental solutions (Bai et al., 2018). Along these lines, politicians are calling for landscape planners and managers to develop solutions for urban climate resilience that draw on an integrated approach to social, cultural, digital, and nature-based solutions (European Commission, 2015). UGI, including urban trees, parks, blue and green open spaces, and green walls and roofs, as a “nature-based solution” to urban climate resilience (Eggermont et al., 2015).

Yet the nature, quality and delivery of UGI is greatly influenced by political considerations, not only at the municipal level but also within the “nested” context of urban environmental planning and governance from the local to trans-national level (Laforteza et al., 2013). In this sense, the policy and governance processes for planning and implementation of UGI take on a critical role in determining the social, ecological, and economic configuration of urban landscapes. Working with, learning from, and scaling-up “networks of care” in the planning and management of UGI might provide valuable place-based perspectives of local residents affording room for diverse social-cultural understandings and subjective values-driven perspectives. Such steps can inform a more just approach to planning by engaging new and frequently silenced voices in nature based solutions (Nesbitt et al., 2018).

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